

SUPPRESSION OF DELAMINATION IN A GRADIENT STRESS FIELD IN GRAPHITE/EPOXY LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

The effect of the inclusion of film adhesive interlayers on the progression of damage and final failure load of simply-supported graphite/epoxy beam-columns was investigated. This loading configuration results in a gradient stress field. Two basic laminates made of AS4/3501-6 graphite/epoxy, $[\pm 45/0/90_4]_{4S}$ and $[(+45_2/-45_2/0)_2/90_5]_{2S}$, were chosen based on previous results. FM-300M film adhesive layers were placed at the outermost 0/90 ply interface which delaminated under static loading in laminates without the film adhesive interlayers. In these specimens, matrix cracks occur in the 90° plies and are connected by delaminations at the interfaces of the 90° effective ply and the neighboring plies leading eventually to failure mainly via the delamination mechanism. When the film adhesive interlayer is inserted at these interfaces, the delamination at the interface is totally suppressed or at least significantly delayed and inhibited. The final failure is therefore dominated by in-plane mechanisms in the major load-carrying plies resulting in an increase in the ultimate load-carrying capability of these specimens by up to 90% over those specimens without the interlayers. After accounting for the increase in bending stiffness due to the increased thickness, an increase of up to 50% in load-carrying capability can still be attributed to the presence of the interlayers.

Keywords: Damage progression, delamination, gradient field, delamination suppression.

1. INTRODUCTION

Delamination is an important failure mode in composite laminates. Delamination refers to the failure of the interply matrix layer and is caused by interlaminar stresses [1] which arise due to the compliance mismatch between plies at free edges [2] or in any gradient stress field [3]. The occurrence of delamination can directly lead to structural failure or can cause an interaction and combination with other damage modes to cause final failure at loads well below those achievable if only in-plane damage and failure mechanisms are at work [4,5]. There is, therefore, an impetus to find methods to suppress delamination.

Various techniques have been successfully employed to suppress and/or delay delamination [6,7]. The most effective of these appears to be the use of a compliant layer such as film adhesive cocured between the plies of a laminate where delamination is likely to occur. The success of this technique has been explained by its ability to reduce the interlaminar stress state at the ply interface [8] as well as by its ability to increase the strength/delamination fracture toughness of the interface region [9,10]. However, this and other techniques have predominantly been used for the suppression of delamination at straight free edges of composite coupons [e.g. 7,8,9,11] or in the case of impact [e.g. 12]. Such work has not been extended to the general application of a gradient stress field, such as a bending field, as would be encountered in many aerospace structural applications and where ply cracking and splitting can synergistically act with delamination to reduce the overall load-carrying capability of the structure.

The primary objective of the current study is, thus, to experimentally study the progression of damage and final failure of laminates with compliant interply film adhesive layers as subjected to a gradient stress field via bending. This damage development is to be compared to that which occurs in similar laminates without the film adhesive interlayers in order to determine the ability of the interlayers to inhibit delamination and to increase the load-carrying capability of the structural configuration.

2. APPROACH

The current work built on previous work on the progression of damage in simply-supported beam-column specimens under quasi-static and cyclic loading [13,14]. The specimen configuration and test jig used in the previous work, shown in Figure 1, was adopted for this investigation. The specimen has a length of 200 mm and a width of 37.5 mm.

The configuration provides a combined axial and bending stress field (thus the use of the term beam-column) as the test jig loads the specimen 2.54 mm off the specimen centerline. This loading eccentricity also allows any friction in the jig to be overcome so that simply-supported response occurs. Furthermore, the magnitude of the eccentricity is greater than possible manufacturing imperfections in the laminates thus making the response insensitive to these imperfections. The total length of the column including the 200 mm test specimen and end pieces is 224 mm.

Besides providing the desired gradient stress field, the specimen meets three important requirements. One, the stress state is relatively simple in that it varies sinusoidally in the longitudinal direction and linearly through-the-thickness (ignoring transverse shear effects). Two, the location of the damage is predictable in that the maximum stress occurs at the longitudinal center of the specimen, away from the points of load introduction. And three, the damage progression is observable since matrix cracks and delamination are evident at the free edges of the specimen.

Two basic configurations of laminates were chosen: $[\pm 45/0/90_4]_{4S}$ and $[(+45_2/-45_2)/0]_2/90_5]_{2S}$. These laminates, used in the previous work, model laminates commonly used in the aerospace industry with 0° , $\pm 45^\circ$, and 90° orientations. Relatively large effective ply thicknesses were utilized to enhance the ability to observe the initiation and progression of damage as manifested by matrix cracks. Groups of plies with the same fiber orientations behave as a single ply in that a matrix crack will propagate through the entire thickness of the ply and delaminations do not occur within such a ply group. Such a group of plies is therefore considered a single "effective ply" [15].

Figure 1. Configuration of (left) test specimen, and (right) specimen in test jig.

All specimens were made from Hercules AS4/3501-6 graphite/epoxy with a nominal per ply thickness of 0.134 mm. The film adhesive utilized was American Cyanamid FM-300M with a nominal thickness of 0.203 mm. Each of these materials has a basic cure temperature of 177°C. For each of the two basic laminate configurations, two different placements of film adhesive interlayers were utilized. The previous work [13,14] indicated that the outermost 0/90 interface was the first to delaminate for both configurations. Thus, a film adhesive interlayer was placed there, consisting of two plies of film adhesive, resulting in arrangements of $[\pm 45/0/FA_2^*/90_4/(\pm 45/0/90_4)_3]_S$ and $[(+45_2/-45_2/0)_2/FA_2/90_5/(+45_2/-45_2/0)_2/90_5]_S$. In the second configuration, a second film adhesive layer was placed at the outermost interface(s) between plies of different orientation: -45/0 for the first basic laminate and the +45/-45 and -45/0 interfaces for the second. This resulted in arrangements of $[\pm 45/FA/0/FA_2/90_4/(\pm 45/0/90_4)_3]_S$ and $[(+45_2/FA/-45_2/FA/0/+45_2/-45_2/0/FA_2/90_5/(+45_2/-45_2/0)_2/90_5)]_S$. Although these interfaces (+45/-45 and -45/0) did not delaminate in the static loading of the basic configurations, it was felt that suppression of delamination at the 0/90 interface could result in delamination at these other interfaces. In addition, specimens subjected to cyclic loading did sometimes delaminate at these interfaces [14].

A test program was designed to determine the damage accumulation history of the four configurations with film adhesive interlayers. The basic configurations without interlayers were not tested since sufficient data was available from the previous work. Specimens of each layout were tested statically to failure. These tests were interrupted and edge replicas taken such that a damage accumulation history could be pieced together. Center deflection versus load measurements were also recorded in order to provide comparative measures of the specimen stiffness for the various configurations. Final failure loads were recorded and the failure mode characterized.

3. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

A total of six specimens of each laminate configuration were manufactured. Laminates (350 mm by 305 mm) of each configuration were cured in an autoclave under 0.59 MPa pressure and full vacuum (760 mm Hg) following the manufacturer's recommended cycle of one hour at 116°C followed by two hours at 177°C. All laminates were postcured in an unpressurized oven for eight hours at 177°C. Each laminate was machined into 37.5 mm by 200 mm specimens using a water-cooled diamond-grit cutting wheel. The specimen edges were polished with a 25 mm diameter felt bob soaked in a colloidal solution of Kaoplite SF, a mild abrasive with an average particle size of 0.7 μm .

All tests were carried out on an MTS 810 Materials Testing System in a quasi-static fashion at a stroke rate of 0.254 mm per second. Three specimens of each configuration were tested monotonically to failure with the load versus center deflection (as measured by a deflection transducer) recorded by computer. For the other three specimens, tests were conducted using the Load Drop Technique [16] where the detection of a drop in compressive load is interpreted as the possible occurrence of damage and the test is therefore stopped. Edge replicas of the specimen were taken at each load drop while the specimen was still under load. Previous work [13] indicated that the development of damage across the width of the specimen was relatively uniform negating the need to perform additional examination in this work. The specimens were reloaded after completion of the edge replicating process.

A microscope, at a magnification of thirty, was used to examine the replicas. When these replicas are examined under a microscope with backlighting, matrix cracks and delaminations can easily be observed. The damage as seen on the replicas was transcribed to schematics of the specimen edge with cracks and delaminations drawn on the appropriate plies. A photograph of a typical replica along with the corresponding transcription is shown in Figure 2. The key shown in Figure 3 is used for all cases. The damage was generally symmetric about the longitudinal centerline, so only the left half of transcriptions are subsequently shown. The side of the specimen exhibiting the greatest tensile stresses, due to bending, is referred to as the tension side and is placed at the top of each replica, with the other side referred to as the compression side.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The characteristics of the damage progression are first compared for the current cases with the inclusion of film adhesive interlayers and those from the previous work [13,14]. This includes characteristics manifested in the post-mortem failure. Comparisons are then made based on the failure load attained.

* FA indicates film adhesive interlayer.

Figure 2. Typical (*left*) edge replica, and (*right*) its transcription.

4.1 Damage Progression and Final Failure

The damage progression for the $[\pm 45/0/90_4]_{4S}$ laminate without film adhesive interlayers is shown in Figure 4 [14]. This is characterized by the initiation of matrix crack in the outermost tension-side 90° ply followed by short, discontinuous delaminations which link these matrix cracks at the $0/90$ interface. These delaminations subsequently grow to form one continuous delamination. In the specimens with film adhesive interlayers, shown in Figures 5 and 6, damage once again initiated as matrix cracks in the outermost tension-side 90° ply. As the load increased, further 90° ply cracking occurred with some cracks extending into the neighboring (lower side) 45° ply. However, generally no delamination occurred at the $0/90$ interface where the film adhesive was placed. In the cases where delamination did occur, it was very minor and tended to extend only between two or three cracks unlike the case where no film adhesive interlayers were used and the delamination became continuous at that interface.

Similar damage characteristics were observed in the $[(+45_2/-45_2)/0_2/90_5]_{2S}$ laminate without film adhesive interlayers, as shown in Figure 7 [14], as matrix cracking initiated in the outermost tension-side 90° effective ply. Short, discontinuous delaminations subsequently formed at the $0/90$ interface linking these cracks and eventually grew and became continuous. Some discontinuous delaminations also occurred later in the loading at the $90/+45$ interface linking matrix cracks. In the specimens with film adhesive interlayers, shown in Figures 8 and 9, the damage again initiated in the outermost tension-side 90° ply in the form of matrix cracks. These cracks subsequently entered the neighboring film adhesive interlayer and 45° ply. Some delaminations were observed at the $0/90$, $90/+45$, and $+45/-45$ interfaces, but these were generally limited to extending between two neighboring matrix cracks.

In addition to the ability of the film adhesive interlayers to suppress/inhibit delamination, the crack spacing in the 90° ply prior to failure, the saturation crack spacing, was increased with the inclusion of film adhesive interlayers. This is apparent by comparing the last edge replica before failure for the cases of laminates without film adhesive interlayers with those having such layers. The results show that the average saturation crack spacing was 0.83 mm for the $[\pm 45/0/90_4]_{4S}$ laminate without interlayers and 1.85 mm for the two configurations with the interlayers. In the $[(+45_2/-45_2)/0_2/90_5]_{2S}$ laminate, the average saturation crack spacing was 1.25 mm for specimens without

Figure 3. Key for all replica transcriptions.

Figure 4 Damage history of a typical $[\pm 45/0/90_4]_4S$ specimen without film adhesive interlayers.

Figure 5 Damage history of a typical $[\pm 45/0/FA_2/90_4/(\pm 45/0/90_4)_3]_5S$ specimen.

Figure 6 Damage history of a typical $[\pm 45/FA/0/FA_2/90_4/(\pm 45/0/90_4)_3]_5S$ specimen.

Figure 7 Damage history of a typical $[(+45_2/-45_2/0)_2/90_5]_2S$ specimen without film adhesive interlayers.

Figure 8 Damage history of a typical $[(+45_2/-45_2/0)_2/FA/90_5/(+45_2/-45_2/0)_2/90_5]_5S$ specimen.

Figure 9 Damage history of a typical $[(+45_2/FA/-45_2/FA/0/+45_2/-45_2/0/FA_2/90_5)/(+45_2/-45_2/0)_2/90_5]_S$ specimen.

interlayers and 1.80 mm for those with interlayers. The ability of film adhesive interlayers to reduce the density of matrix cracking has previously been observed [9,12]. It should also be noted that the additional film adhesive interlayers placed at the ply interfaces above the critical interface in two of the configurations did not appear to play a role in the damage accumulation (and final load-carrying capability as discussed in the next section).

The specimens without film adhesive interlayers generally failed by delamination which caused a sharp reduction in bending stiffness and load-carrying ability. Failure of the major load-carrying 0° plies was generally not involved. This is in direct contrast to the specimens investigated in the current work with film adhesive interlayers where failure involved substantial in-plane mechanisms and virtually no delamination. This contrast can be seen in Figure 10 where two failed $[\pm 45/0/90_4]_4S$ specimens, one without film adhesive and one with film adhesive, are pictured. In the former, delamination failure occurs on the tension and compression sides of the specimen, while in the latter, in-plane failure, with small amounts of delamination involved, occurs on the tension side of the specimen.

Figure 10 Typical failed (left) $[\pm 45/0/90_4]_4S$ specimen without film adhesive interlayers, and (right) $[(\pm 45/0/FA_2/90_4)/(\pm 45/0/90_4)_3]_S$ specimen.

4.2 Failure Loads

The average final failure loads for the laminates with film adhesive interlayers are shown in Table 1 along with those for the base laminates [17]. There is a substantial increase in the load-carrying capability in all cases ranging from 63% to 90% over the base laminates. However, this cannot all be attributed to the ability of the film adhesive interlayers to suppress delamination. There were substantial increases in the thicknesses of the laminates with film adhesive, as shown in Table 2, which has a significant effect on the load-carrying capacity particularly in a bending field.

It is expected that the inclusion of the film adhesive interlayers will increase the thickness of the laminates. However, this increase should be in the range of 1.0 to 1.5 mm depending on the laminate whereas the increase is between 2 to 3.5 mm. Microscopic examination of the edges of the specimen indicates that the film adhesive layers generally attained their nominal thickness of 0.203 mm. However, this examination also indicated that the graphite/epoxy layers generally had a thickness of approximately 0.16 mm as compared to their nominal value of 0.134 mm. Retention of extra matrix, as evidenced by a reduced epoxy flow in the bleeder plies during cure, is a likely cause of this. This

Table 1. Failure Loads^a

Basic Laminate	Film Adhesive Configurations		
	none ^b	two layers at first 0/90 interface only	two layers at first 0/90 interface and one layer at interfaces above
[±45/0/90 ₄] _{4S}	710 (7.1%) ^c	1170 (5.2%)	1160 (4.0%)
[(+45 ₂ /-45 ₂ /0) ₂ /90 ₅] _{2S}	840 (8.2%)	1480 (5.3%)	1600 (4.6%)

^a All loads in N.

^b Values taken from Reference [17].

^c Numbers in parentheses are coefficients of variation.

Table 2. Laminate Thicknesses^a

Basic Laminate	Film Adhesive Configurations		
	none ^b	two layers at first 0/90 interface only	two layers at first 0/90 interface and one layer at interfaces above
[±45/0/90 ₄] _{4S}	7.45	9.78	10.36
[(+45 ₂ /-45 ₂ /0) ₂ /90 ₅] _{2S}	7.88	10.40	11.69

^a All thicknesses in mm.

^b Values taken from Reference [17].

may be attributable to the inclusion of the film adhesive layers, although this has not been observed by previous investigators. Two additional factors are different in the current investigation. The specimens have a larger number of plies than those previously investigated and the film adhesive utilized was three years old whereas the nominal shelf life of this material is one year. It is not known what effects this may have.

It was therefore necessary to account for the increase in specimen thickness in the base load-carrying capability. This was done utilizing laminated plate theory and inputting the baseline properties of the graphite/epoxy and film adhesive. However, the per ply thickness of the graphite/epoxy was increased by 19% to 0.160 mm. This will overcompensate for the effect since the ply modulus properties will also change as the ply thickness, and thus the fiber volume fraction, changes. However, this calculation yields an upper bound on the effect. These calculations showed an increase in the principal bending stiffness, D_{11} , in the vicinity of 100%, and a commensurate decrease in the bending deflection of 50%. This compares with decreases in measured values of bending deflection of 25% to 40%. Thus, the calculation likely overestimates the effect by 20% to 50%.

In order to get a final assessment of the effect of the thickness increase on the load-carrying capability, the ply stresses in the outermost ply and in the outermost 0° ply were calculated for the nominal and increased thickness cases. The increased thickness cases showed a 30% to 38% reduction in these stresses. Since failure in these laminates were dominated by in-plane mechanisms, an increase in load-carrying capability due to increased thickness is inversely related to the decrease in in-plane stresses in the most highly-stressed ply (the outer plies). The inverse of these decreases suggest an increase in load-carrying ability due to the increased thickness of between 50% and 60%. However, since the load-deflection measurements indicated that these calculations for increased thickness overestimated the effect by 20% to 50%, the likely percentage of increased load-carrying capability due to the increased thickness is in the range of 25% to 45%. This indicates that a substantial fraction of the observed increase in load-carrying capability is still attributable to the use of film adhesive and its ability to suppress/inhibit delamination.

5. SUMMARY

An investigation was conducted to determine the effect that the insertion of film adhesive interlayers has on the damage propagation and load-carrying capability of graphite/epoxy laminates subjected to gradient stress fields. Simply-supported beam-columns were utilized to obtain a bending field which also varied along the length of the specimen. Two basic laminates were chosen based on previous work and manufactured from Hercules AS4/3501-6 graphite/epoxy: $[\pm 45/0/90_4]_4S$ and $[(+45_2/-45_2/0)_2/90_5]_2S$. American Cyanamid FM-300M film adhesive was placed at the outermost 0/90 interfaces which delaminated in previous work on specimens without such interfaces. Another set of specimens was manufactured with additional film adhesive interfaces at outer interfaces between the $+45^\circ$, -45° , and 0° plies.

The final failure loads of the specimens with film adhesive interlayers were increased by up to 90% over those specimens without film adhesive interlayers. Despite the fact that the increased ply thickness allowed the base laminates to carry increased load in this bending application, it is still clear that the use of film adhesive interlayers has an important role to play in increasing the load-carrying capability in these configurations. This is evidenced by the calculations done to assess the role of the increased thickness which indicate that the increase in load-carrying capability due to the inclusion of the film adhesive interlayers is as high as 50%, as well as by the scenarios of damage progression and final failure. In all cases, the film adhesive interlayers were able to significantly delay/inhibit delamination and in some cases totally suppress it. This also resulted in a significant decrease in the density of matrix cracking. This was finally manifested in a failure which was dominated by in-plane failure mechanisms. Since the major load-carrying components of the composite, the fiber, were allowed to carry load up to their capability, the overall structural load-carrying ability was increased over the situations where significant delamination uncouples the plies and results in a reduced load-carrying capability. In addition, the film adhesive utilized in this program was three years old whereas the storage life is only one year. This indicates that an even greater advantage can be gained by the use of film adhesive interlayers.

The current work indicates that placement only at critical interfaces, those which are likely to delaminate, are sufficient to have a substantial effect on the damage propagation and load-carrying capability. The added weight due to the inclusion of these film adhesive interlayers is therefore minimized and is well outweighed by the increase in load-carrying capability. It is furthermore suggested that similar gains can be achieved in the cyclic load regime, both in terms of maximum loads as well as in terms of lifetime by suppressing/inhibiting the delamination damage mode in structures subjected to gradient stress fields.

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